

Fig. 2. Tautomers of 1,3-diketone : (a) and (b) ; metal 1,3-diketonate : (c).

The addition of a concentrated metal salt solution to an aqueous methanolic or aqueous ethanolic solution of fluorinated 1,3-diketones results in precipitation of metal chelates.

The metal salts usually used are acetate, nitrate, oxalate, oxychloride and chloride. The other well-known methods for preparing such compounds have been reviewed by us¹⁸. Some of the metal-diketonates studied by us are those derived from Cu²⁺, Cr³⁺, Eu³⁺, Sm³⁺, Tb³⁺ and Gd³⁺.

Quasi-aromatic character :

According to Collman *et al*¹⁶ and other workers¹⁷, each chelate ring in metal 1,3-diketonates has a cyclic π -orbital, formed by the overlapping of vacant d-orbital of the central metal atom of the 1,3-diketonate. These systems have been found to undergo typical electrophilic substitution reactions of the hydrogen atom linked to sp³ hybridized carbon atom and the metal 1,3-diketonates have been termed as quasi-aromatic.

The presence of a perfluoroalkyl group, with its accompanying inductive effect, makes electrophilic substitution slower and requires forcing conditions. We have been able to accomplish this in case of fluorinated 1,3-diketonato chromium derivatives

synthesised by us and chloro-, bromo- and nitro-substituents have been introduced at the central carbon atom of the chelate ring under carefully controlled conditions¹⁸ (Scheme 1).

The quasi-aromaticity of transition metal 1,3-diketonates is well established by now but the quasi-aromatic nature of lanthanide 1,3-diketonate is not investigated. We have, therefore, investigated this problem¹⁹⁻²¹ and have reported that like the transition metal 1,3-diketonates, the lanthanide 1,3-diketonato system also behaves like a sensitive heterocycle possessing some aromatic character (Scheme 2).

On the basis of results obtained, it can be stated that the degree of delocalisation of π -electrons in lanthanide 1,3-diketonates is more pronounced than in the transition metal system leading to enhanced quasi-aromaticity.

The methine proton at the central carbon atom of the chelate ring has been subjected to nitration, chlorination and bromination. Substitution in the phenyl ring is unlikely because of ring deactivation from electron release resonance effects. The disappearance of the C-H in-plane bending vibration band from the region 1225-1180 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectra and the disappearance of the methine resonance signal from the region δ 6.2 ppm in the pmr spectra provide strong evidence for electrophilic substitution at the central carbon atom.

Ar = 4-FC₆H₄, or a derivative ; X = Cl, Br, or NO₂ ; R = Me, Et, Prⁿ, CF₃, or Ph.

Scheme 1

Ar = Fluoroaryl group ; R = CH₃, C₂H₅, CF₃, C₂F₅, or nC₄F₇ ; X = Cl, Br.

Scheme 2

Laser chelates :

Since Urbain's work²² on the rare earth 1,3-diketones, the chemistry of such compounds has assumed considerable importance because of their practical use as potential laser materials. The first laser action from europium benzoylacetate at 6130 Å was reported by Lempicki and Samelson²³ and Schimitschek²⁴. Bhaumik *et al*²⁵ have shown that laser activity is possible only with tetrakis chelates of rare earth and not with *tris* chelates. One of the more successful ligands, so far investigated is benzoyltrifluoroacetone. Its tetrakis derivative, $\text{Eu}(\text{BTFA})_4\text{Q}$, where Q is a cation (Fig. 3), has been shown to lase in acetonitrile solution from 77K to an unusually high temperature (i.e. room temperature). We have studied^{26,27} new tetrakis rare earth chelate salts of the type piperidinium⁺ $[(\text{ArCOCHCOR})_4\text{M}]^-$ (where Ar = fluorophenyl or substituted fluorophenyl, R = alkyl, aryl or perfluoromethyl and M = La^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} and Eu^{3+}). Some of these complexes have been examined for their fluorescence in the solid state at 77K. The ${}^5\text{D}_0 \rightarrow {}^7\text{F}_3$ (at 6173 Å) is by far the most intense transition in case of europium chelates accounting for approximately 95% of the total emission in all europium chelates. It may be noted that this is the first case of piperidinium tetrakis-europium-1,3-diketones in which the ${}^5\text{D}_2$ level has been observed to fluoresce.

Fig. 3. Ar = Fluoroaryl group ;
R = Alkyl, aryl or perfluoroalkyl group ;
M = Eu^{3+} , Sm^{3+} , Tb^{3+} , Gd^{3+} , La^{3+} , Pr^{3+} or Nd^{3+}
Q = Piperidine.

The terbium complex showed fluorescence at 5800 Å (overlapped with the transition of Eu^{3+}) and 5440 Å, involving ${}^5\text{D}_4 \rightarrow {}^7\text{F}_4$ and ${}^5\text{D}_4 \rightarrow {}^7\text{F}_5$ transitions, respectively. In the samarium complex, fluorescence was observed at 5640 Å due to ${}^4\text{F}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{7/2}$ and at 5980 Å due to ${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{9/2}$. The line emission in the samarium chelate is very faint but distinct from europium line emission. The uv absorption spectra²⁷ reveal two maxima. The first maximum is in the region of 3250-3570 Å and is a bathochromic shift of the 1,3-diketone anion absorption due to coordinated chelate ion formation. This clearly indicates that all four 1,3-diketone molecules are used in chelate formation with the metal ion. The second maximum in the region of 2440-2600 Å may be due to free 1,3-diketone anion whose formation in solution is attributed to ionisation of the original tetrakis chelates as follows :

where L = ligand, M = rare earth metal, HP^+ = piperidinium ion.

NMR shift reagents :

In 1969, Hinckley¹⁰ discovered that the addition of *bis* pyridine adduct of *tris* dipivalomethanato europium, $\text{Eu}(\text{dpm})_3 \cdot 2\text{Py}$ to a carbon tetrachloride solution of cholesterol caused important selective downfield shifts in nmr spectrum of steroid and for obvious reasons, the europium complex was named as "shift reagent". The discovery at once suggested that it could lead to simplification of spectra by removal of signal coincidence and also characterization of nucleus in terms of its geometrical relationship with respect to one or more distant functional groups.

The paramagnetic *tris*-lanthanide(III) chelates of $\text{H}(\text{fod})_3$ and $\text{H}(\text{tfacam})_3$ have been increasingly used as nmr shift reagents since the first report. The chemical property which permits this application is the Lewis acidity possessed by the chelates as a consequence of their coordinative unsaturation. The neutral *tris*-chelates dissolve in organic solvents and form labile adducts with a large variety of nucleophilic substrates. Lewis acidity of these chelates also causes two side interactions which may interfere with their usage as nmr shift reagents.

$\text{Eu}(\text{III})$ chelates of fluorinated 1,3-diketones e.g., $\text{H}(\text{fod})_3$ and $\text{H}(\text{tfacam})_3$ undergo²⁸ much stronger interactions with nucleophiles (ethers, ketones, alcohols, esters and olefins) than similar non-fluorinated $\text{Eu}(\text{III})$ chelates. This is most probably due to the increased acidity of the fluorinated chelates due to a decrease in the basicity of the fluorinated 1,3-diketones, and to increased solubility. $\text{Eu}(\text{fod})_3$ is probably the best overall shift reagent for spectral clarification presently available.

Very recently (1974), a novel and efficient nmr shift reagent, tetrakis(1,1,1-trifluoro-4-phenylbutane-2,4-dionato) uranium, $\text{U}(\text{btfa})_4$, has been prepared²⁹. It is capable of forming adducts with Lewis bases (e.g. Py and *n*-BuOH) and inducing proton shifts of a magnitude similar to those obtained with $\text{Eu}(\text{dpm})_3$.

We have also recently synthesised some new polyfluorinated lanthanide 1,3-diketones³⁰ and have studied their ability to produce shifts³¹ in *n*-hexanol, *n*-heptanol, *n*-dodecanol, *p*-fluoroaniline and *m*-trifluoromethyl aniline. The following compounds have been examined :

- [4,4,5,5,5-Pentafluoro-1-(fluorophenyl) 1,3-pentanedionato]holmium(III).
- [4,4,5,5,6,6,6-Heptafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl) 1,3-hexanedionato]europium(III).
- [4,4,5,5,6,6,6-Heptafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl) 1,3-hexanedionato]praseodymium(III).
- [4,4,5,5,5-pentafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl) 1,3-pentanedionato]praseodymium(III).

It was observed that europium and praseodymium 1,3-diketonates act as the best shift reagents for downfield and upfield shifts, respectively as they do not produce line broadening. Holmium 1,3-diketonates produce maximum shifts with certain nucleophiles but they are not used as shift reagents due to line broadening.

As reaction intermediates for synthesis of bioactive heterocycles :

Apart from the various analytical applications of the 1,3-diketones listed above, we have recently employed these compounds for synthesis of different types of bioactive heterocycles containing fluorinated groups. These heterocycles include pyrazoles, isoxazoles, pyrazolo[1,5-a]pyrimidines, 1,2,4-triazolo[4,3-b]pyridazines, 1H-pyrazolo[3,4-b]pyridines, 1,4-diazepines, 1,5-benzodiazepines, pyrazolo[5,1-c][1,2,4]triazines etc. Some of these compounds have shown promising CNS depressant, antiobesity and anticholinergic activities²¹.

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